

THE ATTITUDES OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS TOWARDS SPORTS: ATTITUDE AND METAPHORICAL PERCEPTION

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Abstract:

The reactions and values that individuals possess towards objects or situations reflect their attitudes. A metaphor is to describe a situation or object by establishing an analogy to another situation or object. The aim of this study is to examine the attitudes and perceptions of undergraduate students studying at various faculties towards sports. The present study, in which a mixed method design was used, was conducted with undergraduate students of Gazi University in the 2017-2018 academic year. In this context, the sample of the study was comprised of a total of 481 (241 female, 240 male) undergraduate students studying at various departments, such as Physical Education Teaching, Banking and Insurance, Political Science and Public Administration, Law, Statistics, Finance, Chemical Engineering, Banking, Conservatory, and Psychological Counseling and Guidance (PCG). Data collection tools were "Demographic Information Form" developed by the researchers, "The Sports-Oriented Attitude Scale" developed by Koçak (2014), and "semi-structured form" prepared by researchers to collect qualitative data. In the analysis of the data, frequency, arithmetic mean, and standard deviation values were calculated and t-test and ANOVA were applied to the quantitative data. Besides, content analysis was applied to the qualitative data. Significant positive correlations were found between the subdimensions of the attitudes of university students towards sports and age. It was found that the subdimensions of the attitudes toward sports showed significant differences in favor of female participants, and the subdimensions of psychosocial development and mental development were found to be significantly different in favor of the students' of departments of teaching. There were significant positive correlations between the subdimensions of the attitudes of university students towards sports and age. In the context of the qualitative data of the study, it was discovered that metaphors obtained from the participants were found to be clustered under the categories as life source, benefit provider, value, food, delighting, professional association, nature, addiction, and necessity. It was concluded

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that the attitudes of university students towards sports were moderate. It was also determined that metaphors for sports were often composed of positive ones.

Keywords: sports, attitude, metaphor, university student

1. Introduction

Nowadays, human beings who look for a healthy and peaceful life, a physically fit appearance, a new social circle, and relaxation, and try to avoid the bad habits and the busy schedule with a desire for emotional satisfaction are inevitably inclined to do sports.

Sports is important to be a phenomenon that regulates personal and social relations though it is done for many different purposes such as competition, pleasure, health, aesthetics, entertainment, game, advertising, propaganda, and science. The basic element of sports is human. Hence, it has become an indispensable social phenomenon nowadays whether it is to raise constructive, creative and healthy young people for the future, or as a means to resist social discrimination and alienation for an efficient society (Yetim, 2011). It also plays an important role in combating stress, which is the modern plague. Since sports make individuals relaxed, happy and enjoyed what they have accomplished (Strong, 2005). In this respect, university students are expected to be inclined to do sports with the desire to deal with daily problems, stress, and troubles in the harmony with the social circle, and the desire to have a physically fit appearance and peace. In this context, the concept of "attitude" is critical because it is the basis for the university students to be able to be inclined to do sports.

Attitudes are certain affective factors that shape the behaviors of people and affect the direction and intensity of these behaviors (Doydu, Çelen and Çoknaz, 2013). The emergence of the attitudes, the influence of them on the behaviors of the individuals, and the attitude change within a certain period have always attracted the attention of the scientific world and have been the subject of many studies (Tekkurşun Demir, Cicioğlu, İlhan and Arslan, 2017). Learned tendencies that lead people to show certain behaviors in the face of others, objects and conditions imply the definition of attitude (Demirhan and Altay, 2001). According to Freedman, Sears and Carlsmith (2003), attitude is a permanent system including a behavioral tendency and cognitive and emotional elements towards a particular object, idea or person. Organizations covering enthusiasm, cognition and learning processes in the perception of a person (Güllü and Güçlü, 2009), and the phenomena that are acquired by learning, shape the behavior of the individual and cause bias in the decision-making process are called as attitude (Özgüven, 2005). Attitude towards an object, event, or person can be positive and negative. If the acquired attitude is positive, it is more likely to perform the behavior, whereas if the acquired attitude is negative, it is less likely to perform the behavior (Özgüven, 2005). Therefore, it can be said that what mobilizes the individual to perform any behavior and the magnitude of the desire to perform that behavior are

related to attitude. In addition to revealing attitudes towards sports, identifying the metaphors towards sports is another important research topic.

A metaphor is a perfect technique that makes the conceptual knowledge more powerful. A concept can be described with more than one phrase with the help of a metaphor. According to Morgan (1998), the use of metaphors is a way of thinking and understanding the world. People try to explain how they see life, environment, events, and objects by using different metaphors (Cerit, 2008).

It is important for university students, who play an important role in the raising of the next generation, to determine their attitudes towards sports and express how they perceive sports with metaphors. In this context, it was aimed to determine the attitudes and metaphorical perceptions of undergraduate students studying at various faculties towards sports.

2. Methodology

2.1. Design of the Study

A mixed method design was used in the present study. According to Creswell (2008), the basic assumption of mixed method studies is that the use of qualitative and quantitative research methods together enables the research problem and questions to be better understood than the separate use of these methods. The survey method was used in the quantitative stage of the study while the semi-structured form was used in the qualitative stage.

2.2. Sample

The sample of the study was comprised of a total of 481 (241 female, 240 male) undergraduate students studying at various departments of Gazi University in Ankara during the spring semester of 2017-2018 education. Participants were from Physical Education Teaching (13 female, 37 male), Banking and Insurance (47 female, 2 male), Political Science and Public Administration (17 female, 35 male), Law (24 female, 26 male), Statistics (12 female, 37 male), Finance (22 female, 19 male), Chemical Engineering (31 female, 19 male), Banking (18 female, 29 male), Conservatory (17 female, 26 male), and PCG (40 female, 10 male).

2.3. Data Collection Tools

Data collection tools were comprised of "Demographic Information Form", "The Sports-Oriented Attitude Scale", and "semi-structured form" prepared by researchers to collect qualitative data

A. Demographic Information Form

The information about the participants, such as age, gender, department, year of study, doing exercise in past life, and doing regular exercise, was collected with the help of the demographic information form developed by the researchers.

B. The Sports-Oriented Attitude Scale

In this study, "The Sports-Oriented Attitude Scale" was used. The scale was developed by Koçak (2014) and is comprised of 22 items and 3 subdimensions which are psychosocial development, physical development, and mental development. The loading values of the items range from .452 to .850. Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient and Spearman-Brown internal consistency coefficient were used to test the reliability of the scale and these values were calculated as .86 and .88, respectively.

C. Semi-Structured Form

Metaphors were obtained using a semi-structured form. To determine the perceptions of the participants on the concept of sports, they were asked to complete the statement "Sports is like because" and write and explain the words that appear in their minds with the concept of sports.

2.4. Data Analysis

Parametric tests were applied to the data after it was determined that the skewness and kurtosis values of the data were within ± 1 . In this context, frequency, arithmetic mean, standard deviation, t-test and ANOVA were used in the analysis of the quantitative data.

"Content analysis" was performed to analyze the qualitative data. The content analysis method enables a researcher to make interpretation through the statistical data. The use of statistical data allows the researcher to make a systematic and objective interpretation (Koçak and Arun, 2006). In this context, the data were analyzed in four stages: coding of the data, determining the themes of the encoded data, the organization of codes and themes, identification and interpretation of the findings (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2011). The data obtained by the metaphor technique were digitized and expressed as frequency. Similar items in the statements were grouped and categorized appropriately. At the next stage, to ensure the reliability of the study, an expert opinion was received to confirm whether the themes obtained represented codes. The field expert was asked to match the codes with the themes. The percentage of agreement formula of Miles and Huberman (1994) was used for the reliability of the study by comparing the matches made by the field expert with the matches made by the researchers. Accordingly, the percentage of agreement was calculated as 90%. Thus, it was found that a certain level of reliability was provided.

4. Findings

Table 1: The relationship between age and the attitude towards sports

Variable	Age	Psychosocial Development	Physical Development	Mental Development	X	ss
Age	1	,04	-,00	,00	21,69	2,67

The findings of the Pearson Moment Correlation Test between the Sports-Oriented Attitude Scale and age are presented in Table 1. As a result of the analysis, no significant difference was found between age and the subdimensions of the scale ($p < .05$).

Table 2: Independent Group T-Test Results on Gender

Variable	Gender	N	$\bar{x}$	Ss	df	T	p
Psychosocial Development	Female	241	47,67	6,69	479	2,89	,00*
	Male	240	45,49	9,55			
Physical Development	Female	241	25,91	3,82	479	3,13	,00*
	Male	240	24,62	5,06			
Mental Development	Female	241	14,67	3,18	479	-,11	,00*
	Male	240	14,66	3,49			

* $p < .05$

According to the independent groups t-test, significant differences were found between gender and psychosocial development ($t=2.89$; $p < 0.05$), physical development ($t=3.13$; $p < .05$), and mental development ($t=-.11$; $p < .05$). Therefore, it was found that the mean scores of female participants ($\bar{x}=47.67$, $\bar{x}=24.91$, $\bar{x}=14.67$) were higher than of male participants ($\bar{x}=45.49$, $\bar{x}=24.62$, $\bar{x}=14.66$) in all subdimensions, respectively. The differences between the scores were found to be significant.

Table 3: ANOVA Results on Departments

Department	N	$\bar{x}$	Sources of Variance	SS	MS	F	p	Significant Difference	
Psychosocial Development	Physical Education teaching	50	49,24	Between-groups	1290,705	143,412	2,120	,02*	Physical Education Teaching* - Banking-Chemical Engineering
	Banking and Insurance	49	45,48						
	Political Science	52	47,17						
	Law	50	46,98	Within-group	31861,964	67,647			
	Statistics	49	45,79						
	Finance	41	47,39						
	Chemical Engineering	50	48,60						
	Banking	47	43,19						
	Conservatory	43	45,58						
PCCG	50	46,16							
Physical Development	Physical Education teaching	50	25,48	Between-groups	194,127	21,570	1,054	,39	-
	Banking and Insurance	49	25,55						
	Political Science	52	25,15						
	Law	50	25,48	Within-group	9635,195	20,457			
	Statistics	49	25,89						
	Finance	41	26,09						
	Chemical	50	25,14						

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Engineering									
	Banking	47	23,85						
	Conservatory	43	24,37						
	PCG	50	25,66						
Mental Development	Physical Education teaching	50	16,36	Between-groups	291,314	32,368	3,009	,00*	Physical Education Teaching*-Banking and Insurance- Banking- PCG
	Banking and Insurance	49	14,24						
	Political Science	52	14,75	Within-group	5066,894	10,758			
	Law	50	14,36						
	Statistics	49	14,32						
	Finance	41	14,80						
	Chemical Engineering	50	15,00						
	Banking	47	13,97						
	Conservatory	43	15,30						
		PCG	50	13,38					

*p<,05

The results presented in Table 3 shows that statistically significant differences were found between departments of the students and psychosocial development ($F=2.120$; $p<.05$) and mental development ($F=3.009$; $p<.05$). Post-Hoc test (Tukey HSD) was conducted to determine the source of the significant differences between groups. The groups having higher score differences are shown with the symbol (*). In the subdimension psychosocial development, it was determined that the mean score of the participants studying at the department of physical education teaching ($\bar{x}=49.24$) was significantly higher than of the participants studying at the departments of banking ($\bar{x}=43.19$) and chemical engineering ($\bar{x}=48.60$). In the subdimension of mental development, it was found that the mean score of the participants studying at the department of physical education teaching ($\bar{x}=16.36$) was significantly higher than of the participants studying at the departments of banking and insurance ($\bar{x}=14.24$), banking ($\bar{x}=13.97$) and PCG ($\bar{x}=13.38$).

Table 4. ANOVA Results on the Year of Study

Subdimensions	Year of Study	N	$\bar{x}$	Source of Variance	SS	MS	F	P	Significant Difference
Psychosocial Development	1 st year	114	46,38	Between groups	583,152	194,384	2,847	,03*	2-4*
	2 nd year	177	45,68						
	3 rd year	63	45,87	Within-group	32569,518	68,280			
	4 th year	127	48,37						
Physical Development	1 st year	114	25,73	Between groups	51,898	17,299	,844	,47	-
	2 nd year	177	25,34						
	3 rd year	63	24,73	Within-group	9777,424	20,498			
	4 th year	127	25,02						

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Mental Development	1 st year	114	15,04	Between groups	108,565	36,188	3,288	,02*	1*-2
	2 nd year	177	14,02						
	3 rd year	63	14,98	Within-group	5249,643	11,006			
	4 th year	127	14,93						

*p<,05

The ANOVA results in Table 4 shows that statistically significant differences were found between the year of study and psychosocial development (F=2.847; p<0.05) and mental development (F=3.288; p<.05). Post-Hoc test (Tukey HSD) was conducted to determine the source of the significant differences between groups. The groups having higher score differences are shown with the symbol (*). In the subdimension of psychosocial development, it was determined that the mean score of the 4th year students ($\bar{x}$ =48.37) was significantly higher than of 2nd year students ($\bar{x}$ =45.68). In the subdimension of mental development, it was found that the mean score of the 1st year students ($\bar{x}$ =15.04) was significantly higher than of the 2nd year students ($\bar{x}$ =14.02).

Table 5: Independent Group T-Test Results on Doing Regular Exercise

Variable	Doing Regular Exercise	N	$\bar{x}$	ss	df	T	p
Psychosocial Development	Yes	292	47,90	8,32	473	4,53	,00*
	No	183	44,40	7,95			
Physical Development	Yes	292	25,65	4,33	473	2,39	,00*
	No	183	24,63	4,81			
Mental Development	Yes	292	14,99	3,43	473	3,06	,00*
	No	183	14,03	3,09			

*p<,05

According to Table 5, significant differences were found between doing regular exercise and psychosocial development (t=4.53; p<.05), physical development (t=2.39; p<.05) and mental development (t=3.06; p<.05). Therefore, it was found that the mean scores of those who do regular exercise ($\bar{x}$ =47.90, $\bar{x}$ =25.65, $\bar{x}$ =14.99) were higher than of those who do not do regular exercise ($\bar{x}$ =44.40, $\bar{x}$ =24.63, $\bar{x}$ =14.03) in all subdimensions, respectively.

Table 6: The categories of metaphors generated by the participants towards sports

Categories	Metaphor subject	Frequency	Metaphor source "Sports is like...."
Life Source	water (28), love (16), happiness (10), meal (7), need (2), breath (1), passion (1), sleeping (1), sun (1), life (1).	68	"...water. Because how the waterless tree dries up and loses productivity, the man without sports loses efficiency in the same way (K123)." ".....love. Because once you're fallen, you can never abandon (K451)." ".....happiness. Because happiness is the source of life

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			(K276)."
Benefit Provider	Health (17), medicine (15), life(7), lifestyle (6), farming(3), rolling stone (2), order (2), laughter (2), engine (2), plaster (2), thinking (2), pencil (1), awareness (1).	62	"...health. Because there is no disease that sports cannot cure (K187)." ".....medicine. Because it is good for health (K341)." ".....laughter. Because it makes you burn calories (K195)."
Value Image	determination (10), homeland (7), happiness (6), military service (4), butterfly (3), pet (3), make-up (3), joke (3), time (3), father (3), ethics (2) powder (2), woman (1), game (1), lifestyle (1), fate (1) life (1), glasses (1), my own (1), heart (1), studying at Gazi University (1), insect (1).	59	"....determination. Because it increases in value as you make a great effort on it (K240)." ".....homeland. Because lives are sacrificed for her sake (K22)." ".....a butterfly. Because it makes you grasp the importance of life (K132)."
Food	onion (11), bitter chocolate (9), barbecue (8), dessert (4), pasta (3), chocolate (3), salt-free meal (3), green apple (3), waffle (2), hot pepper (2), pineapple (2), sugar (2), meal(1), bread (1), candied chestnut (1).	55	".....an onion. Because it has grades (K186)." "....bitter chocolate. Because it is bitter and hard (K195)." ".....barbecue. Because it is difficult to do, but delighting (K312)."
Delighting	happiness (10), green and blue (9), meditation (8), laughter(7), peace (6),complementary (4), arts (2), kunefe (1), antidepressant (2),lover (1), hobby (1), therapy (1), worship (1).	53	"..... happiness. Because it gives happiness as it is done(K304)." ".....green and blue. Because they are the colors of peace and happiness (K307)." ".....meditation. Because it delivers inner peace (K289)."
Professional Association	attorney (12), musician(7), jazzmusic (6), geometry (4), politics (4), finance (3), athletics (2), law (2), insurance (2), engineering (1), zero (1), arts (1), Chinese (1), statistics(1), contract (1), music box(1).	50	".....an attorney. Because everyone needs him/her (K257)." ".....jazz music. Because it is not always performed (K227)." ".....a musician. Because it is food of the soul (K165)."
Nature Image	mountain (14), soil (10), air (7), flower (4), river (3), plant (3), cold (1), sea (1), wave (1), violet (1), fire (1) cloud (1), tree (1).	48	".....a mountain. Because you become tough as you do it (K172)." ".....soil. Because what you plant now you will harvest later (K258)." ".....air. Because you cannot live without it (K329)."
Addiction	beer (13), cigarette (11), series (7),		".....beer. Because you

	drugs (4) vine (3), alcohol (2), whiskey (1), rakı (1), bet (1), internet (1), court shoes (1), desire to lose weight(1).	46	cannot quit if you start to do it (K176)." ".....a cigarette. Because you become addicted (K281)." ".....series. Because you wait the next day impatiently (K327)."
Necessity	course (22), discipline (8), getting up early (5), money (1), sleep (1), school (1), exam (1), necessity (1)	40	".....a course. Because you feel like you have to do it although you don't like it (K116)." ".....discipline. Because if you don't do it, you will be in trouble (K101)." ".....getting up early. Because you feel like you have to do it although you don't like it (K92)."

Table 6 lists the metaphors generated by the participants towards sports and the categories of these metaphors. While categorizing the metaphors towards sports, studies that listed similar categories (Arpa, 2014; Bek, 2008; Cudd, 2007; Deniz Çeliker and Akar, 2015; Fişek, 1998; Karakaya and Salici, 2016; Kesici and Muhiç, 2013; Koç, Murathan, Yetiş and Murathan, 2015; Kurtipek and Sönmezoğlu, 2018; Küçük and Koç 2004; Namlı, Temel and Güllü, 2016; Sevinç and Ergenç, 2007; Özsoy, 2011; Segrave, 2000; Yalçın and Enginer, 2012; Yetim, 2015; Zorba, 2012) and different categories (Segrave, 2000) were used. Analysis of the metaphors generated by the participants resulted in 9 categories. It was determined that 8 of these were comprised of positive metaphors and 1 of them was comprised of negative metaphors. The categories with positive metaphors and the highest frequency are Life Source (f=68), Benefit Provider (f=62), Value (f=59), Food (f=55), Delighting (f=50), Professional Association (f=50), Nature Image (f=48), and Addiction (f=46). The only category that contains negative metaphors is Necessity (f=40).

It was determined that the perceptions of the students and the metaphors they generated were clustered under the abovementioned categories.

The category with the highest frequency of responses from the participants related to their perceptions towards sports is "Life Source". In this category, sports was described by the metaphors of "laughter, engine, plaster, thinking, pencil, awareness". As seen in Table 6, the participant with the code K123 associated sports with water and stated "Sports is like water. Because how the waterless tree dries up and loses productivity, the man without sports loses efficiency in the same way."

The other category with the highest frequency of responses is "Benefit Provider". In this category, sports was described by the metaphors of "health, medicine, life, lifestyle, farming, rolling stone, order, laughter, engine, plaster, thinking, pencil, awareness". One of the

participants associated sports with health and stated "*Sports is like health. Because there is no disease that sports cannot cure (K187).*"

Another category is called "Value" (f = 59). In this category, sports was described by the metaphors of "*determination, homeland, happiness, military service, butterfly, pet, make-up, joke, time, father, ethics, powder, woman, game, lifestyle, fate, life, glasses, my own, heart, studying at Gazi University, insect*". One of the participants associated sports with determination and stated "*Sports is like determination. Because it increases in value as you make a great effort in it (K240).*"

In the category of "Food", there are metaphors related to nutrients. The metaphors in this category are "*onion, bitter chocolate, barbecue, dessert, pasta, chocolate, salt-free meal, green apple, waffle, hot pepper, pineapple, sugar, meal, bread, candied chestnut sugar*". One of the participants associated sports with onion and stated "*Sports are like an onion. Because it has grades.*" (K186)

In "Delighting" category, the participants associated sports with happiness-related metaphors. In this context, sports were explained with the metaphors of "*happiness, green and blue, meditation, laughter, peace, complementary, arts, kunefe, antidepressant, lover, hobby, therapy, worship*".

In "Professional Association" category, the participants associated sports to various professions. Accordingly, sports was explained by the metaphors of "*attorney, musician, jazz music, geometry, politics, finance, athletics, law, insurance, engineering, zero, arts, Chinese, statistics, contract, music box*".

Table 6 shows that the category of "Nature Image" is comprised of the metaphors of "*mountain, soil, air, flower, river, plant, cold, sea, wave, violet, cloud, tree*". In this category, sports was explained with the metaphor of "mountain" and one of the participants stated "*Sports is like a mountain. Because you become tough as you do it (K172).*"

The "category of "Addiction" is comprised of the metaphors of "*beer, cigarette, series, drugs, wine, alcohol, whiskey, rakı, bet, internet, court shoes, desire to lose weight*". One of the participants stated "*Sports is like beer. Because you cannot quit if you start to do it.*" (K176)

The category of "Necessity", which is the only negative category in the study, is comprised of the metaphors of "*course, discipline, getting up early, money, sleep, school, exam, necessity*" and one of the participants stated "*Sports is like a course. Because you feel like you have to do it although you don't like it.*" (K116)

5. Discussion and Result

In this context, it was aimed to determine the attitudes and metaphorical perceptions of the undergraduate students. In this context, it was tried to determine the attitudes of the students towards sports in terms of several variables such as age, gender, year of study, doing exercise in past life, and doing regular exercise.

In the study, there was no significant difference between the attitudes of the participants towards sport and age. This can be explained all age groups are aware of

the contributions of sports to mental, emotional, social and psychomotor developments of the human being thanks to the media. Moreover, the ages of the participants are close to each other. When compared to the results of the present study, there are studies in the literature that reached similar (Kangalgil, Hünük, Demirhan, 2006, Türkmen, 2016; Koçak 2014, Türkmen, Abdurahimoğlu, Varol and Gökdağ 2016; Göksel and Caz 2016; Keskin 2015; Tortop, 2005) and different results (Taşğın and Tekin, 2009; Wersch, Trew and Turner, 1992). Significant differences were found between gender and the subdimensions of psychosocial development, physical development, and mental development. Therefore, it can be said that the attitude level of the female participants is higher than of the male counterparts. The desire of women to have a fit and beautiful appearance and live healthier can be attributed to the reason for such a result. There are studies in the literature that reached similar results (Altay and Özdemir 2006; Çelik and Pular, 2011; Güllü, 2007; Kangalgil et al., 2004; Koca and Demirhan, 2004; Koçak, 2014; Koçak and Hümeriç 2006; Kimbal 2007; King 1994; Şişko and Demirhan, 2002; Smoll and Shutz, 1980; Taşğın and Tekin, 2009; Türkmen et al., 2016) and different results (Göksel and Caz, 2016; Koçak, Tuncel and Tuncel 2015; Yanık and Çamlıyer 2015).

On the other hand, significant differences were found between the departments of the students and the subdimensions of psychosocial development mental development. In psychosocial development, it was found the attitude level of the students studying at the department of physical education teaching was significantly higher than of the students studying at the departments of banking and chemical engineering. Besides, in mental development, it was determined the attitude level of the students studying at the department of physical education teaching was significantly higher than of the students studying at the departments of banking and insurance, banking and PCG. It can be argued that the reason for this is that the students of the department of physical education teaching are not only lectured about the importance of sports and its contributions to development but also involved in sports. There are studies in the literature that reached similar (Carlson, 1994; Chung and Philips, 2002; Çelen, 2012; Doydu, Çelen and Çoknaz 2013; Harriet, Richard and Tokie 2006; Park, 1995; Rice, 1988; Schneider and Marriott, 2010) and different results (Yalçınkaya, et al., 2002). In addition, significant differences were found between year of study and psychosocial development and mental development. In the subdimension of psychosocial development, it was determined that the mean score of the 4th year students was significantly higher than of 2nd year students. However, in the subdimension of mental development, it was found that the mean score of the 1st year students was significantly higher than of the 2nd year students. The significant difference in favor of the 4th year students is thought to be related to the issue that they no longer suffer from adaptation to the campus, courses and social circle. While some studies in the literature reached similar results (Altay and Özdemir, 2006; Çetin, 2007; Subramaniam and Silverman, 2007), there are also studies that reached different results (Göksel and Caz, 2016; Şişko and Demirhan, 2002; Tavlaş, 2012; Yıldız, 2010). Significant differences were found between doing regular exercise and the subdimensions of

psychosocial, physical, and mental development. It can be argued that this is caused by the fact that factors such as the desire to maintain the fitness, relax the mind with sports, and maintain discipline and concentration. There are studies in the literature in which similar results were obtained (Alparslan, 2008; Cox et al., 2008; Güllü, 2007; Hünük, 2006; Kangalgil et al., 2004; Kangagil et al., 2006; Singh and Devi 2013; Türkmen et al., 2016).

As a result of the analysis of the metaphors generated by the participant in the qualitative stage of the study, 8 positive and 1 negative categories were obtained. While these positive 8 categories were "life source", "benefit provider", "value", "food", "delighting", "professional association", and "addiction", the negative one was "necessity". Accordingly, the participants in the category of "life source" used the metaphors of water, love, happiness, food, need, breath, passion, sleeping, sun, and life. It can be argued the reason why participants preferred to use abovementioned metaphors is that they consider sports as a promoter of the social-physical-mental development, a key for the healthy life, and an entertainment tool. There are studies in the literature that were conducted with similar categories to ours (Küçük and Koç 2004, Sevinç and Ergenç, 2007). It was observed that the participants associated sports with the metaphors of health, medicine, life, lifestyle, farming, rolling stone, order, laughter, engine, plaster, thinking, pencil, and awareness in the category of "benefit provider". In this context, it can be argued that the metaphors in this category may evoke the contributions and benefits of sports to body functions (Bek, 2008; Fişek, 1998, Yetim, 2015, Zorba, 2012). On the other hand, the participants used the metaphors of determination, homeland, happiness, military service, butterfly, pet, make-up, joke, time, father, ethics, powder, nothing, woman, game, lifestyle, fate, life, studying at Gazi University, heart, my own glasses, and insect in the category of "value". The use of these metaphors can be associated with the positive effects of sports in all development stages and the interests of the participants in sports. There are studies in the literature that reached parallel results (Koç et al., 2015, Sevinç and Ergenç, 2007). The category of "food" cover the metaphors of onion, bitter chocolate, barbecue, dessert, pasta, salt-free meal, chocolate, green apple, waffle, hot pepper, pineapple, sugar, food, bread, candied chestnut. This can be explained by the fact that the participants relate sports to nutrition, which is the basic need in life, and consider bitterness-sweetness of food. The studies with parallel results can be found in the literature (Sevinç and Ergenç, 2007).

The metaphors of happiness, green and blue, meditation, laughter, peace, complementary, antidepressant, arts, kunefe, lover, hobby, therapy, and worship take place in the category of "delighting". In this context, it can be said that sports evokes positive effects on the participants and makes them happy. In the literature, there are several studies of metaphor conducted with similar categories to ours (Arpa, 2014, Karakaya and Salici, 2016). Another category, "professional association", is comprised of the metaphors of attorney, musician, jazz music, geometry, politics, finance, athletics, law, insurance, engineering, zero, arts, statistics, Chinese, contract, and music box. The emergence of this category can be attributed to the fact that the participants associate

sports with their profession. Besides, similar categories are found in the literature (Sevinç and Ergenç, 2007). The category of "nature" is comprised of the metaphors of mountain, soil, air, flower, river, plant, cold, sea, wave, violet, tree, fire, and cloud. It can be said that the participants associate sports with these metaphors in terms of being physically fit and having a healthy appearance. The studies in the literature with similar results support our findings (Deniş, Çeliker and Akar, 2015). In the category of "addiction", there are the metaphors of beer, alcohol, series, drugs, wine, whiskey, rakı, cigarette, court shoes, bet, internet, and desire to lose weight. It can be deduced from this category that the participants regard sports as a habit which is difficult to be abandoned. Similar results are found in the literature (Kurtipek and Sönmezoğlu, 2018). Finally, in the category of "necessity", it was found that the participants described sports with the metaphors of course, discipline, money, sleep, getting up early, school, exam, and necessity. This can be attributed to the fact that the participants consider sports as a task which is obligatory to be done, but not very popular.

Overall, in the quantitative stage of the study, it was determined that there were significant differences between the attitudes of the participants towards sports and gender, department and the year of study. However, no significant difference was found between their attitudes and age. On the other hand, in the qualitative stage of the study, 8 positive and 1 negative categories were obtained. In the light of all these results, it was concluded that the attitudes of the students towards sports are moderate and the metaphors generated by them are generally positive. This can be said to be due to their positive attitudes towards physical education and sports course. In the literature, there are several studies revealing that the positive attitudes of undergraduate students (MacPhail, 2011, Özbakır, Tannehill and Zakrajsek, 1993; Taşmektepligil, Yılmaz, İmamoğlu and Kılıçgil, 2006) and the participants of different age groups (Hünük, 2006) towards physical education and sports course increase positive attitudes towards sports. The positive attitudes and metaphors of the participants towards sports can be attributed to the kindness of physical education teachers, the policies of the Ministry of Youth and Sports for participation in sports, and media which often broadcasts physical, mental, cognitive, and emotional influences of sports.

The attitudes of the university students should be positive towards sports to raise themselves and generations as healthy individuals. In this context, it may be suggested to disseminate the activities which make them participate in sports, increase the number of sports halls, make these sports halls free of charge for university students, facilitate the access to these halls, and make physical education and sports course compulsory in all faculties. In the study in which Tekkurşun-Demir et al. (2017) examined the attitudes of prospective classroom teachers to sports, it is suggested that sports-oriented courses which are taken by primary school teachers, who teach courses related to physical activities and games, for 3 semesters in undergraduate education should be increased to 8 semesters. This is because primary school teachers are critical for students to make sports a habit and it is important for primary school teachers to

have a positive attitude towards physical education course, know its contributions to students and prepare sports activities suitable for students.

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